

Solvation and Free-energies of Transfer of Single ions

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Experimental determinations yield changes of thermodynamic parameters associated with neutral combinations of ions (electrolytes) but offer no means of separation of these into components associated with the constituent ions. Yet 'single ion thermodynamics' is a legitimate branch of physical chemistry. The free energies of transfer of ions from one solvent to another, known as 'medium effect' may throw light on ion-solvent interactions. Further it will lead to a unified emf series, independent of the solvent, referring the standard electrode potential in different solvents to a single arbitrarily chosen point, i.e., in a reference solvent which can conveniently be the standard hydrogen electrode in the reference solvent.

The status of our knowledge towards understanding 'medium effect' or estimation of free energies of transfer single ions has been presented through a brief survey of both theoretical and experimental approaches.

THE importance of the studies of reactions in non-aqueous and mixed solvents has been summarized by Meek¹, Franks^{2,3}, Popovych⁴, Bates^{5,6}, Alexander^{7,8}, Criss and Salomon⁹ and others^{10,11}. The ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions have been subjects of wide interest¹². One of the most important but elusive aspects of the solution chemistry is the determination of 'single ion' thermodynamics or 'medium effects' of ions in mixed and non-aqueous solvents. This would form a basis for explaining quantitatively the influence of the solvent and the extent of interactions of ions in solvents and thus pave the way to a better understanding of the different phenomena associated with solution chemistry.

The experimental methods yield the thermodynamics of transfer of neutral pairs or combinations but offer no means of separating these into single-ion contributions. Nevertheless, according to Strehlow¹³, "single ion thermodynamics is a legitimate branch of Physical Chemistry. This division of thermodynamic functions of electrolytes into single-ion values may reveal correlation between measureable - but from a thermodynamic point of view - unrelated quantities".

Various theoretical and semi-empirical extra-thermodynamic attempts¹⁴⁻¹⁹ have been made to determine single-ion thermodynamics with some success. Because of its wide implications, the state of our knowledge of 'medium effect' of ions has been reviewed by different authors^{4,11,13,20-23} during the last ten to fifteen years. It would,

therefore, be in order to consider the 'medium effect' and related topics afresh.

The entropy and enthalpy changes which accompany the transfer of a chemical entity from one solvent to another are known as "medium effects". In a pioneering work, Owen²⁴ differentiated primary and secondary medium effects. The former is the reversible work of transfer of a mole of ion 'i' from the standard state in solvent '1' (water) to the standard state in solvent '2' ('S') and is often referred to as simply "medium effect". The secondary medium effect is a function of solute concentration and includes ion-ion interactions and solvation. The primary medium effect is expressed by the equation, the terms having the usual meaning.

$$\log^w \gamma_i - \log^s \gamma_i = ({}^s \mu_i^\circ - {}^w \mu_i^\circ) = \Delta G_i^\circ / 2.303RT = \log_m \gamma_i \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

As seen from the expression $\log_m \gamma_i$ is independent of concentration of the species and takes account only of ion-solvent interaction. As such recent work has been concentrated on the primary "medium effect".

Real (absolute) Free energy of solvation :

The real free energy of solvation, $\Delta \mu_i^{25-28}$, is defined as the free energy change of transfer of ionic species i from the gas phase (field free space) into a solution and is expressed by the equation,

$$\alpha_i = \alpha_i^\circ + RT \ln a_i = \mu_i^\circ + Z_i F \chi^s + RT \ln a_i \dots (2)$$

α_i° is the standard free energy of solvation. It has been divided into μ_i° which gives a measure of standard free energy of chemical solvation (ion solvent interaction) and the other $Z_i \chi^s F$, the energy of the ion due to the electrical double layer at the free surface of the solution (χ^s being the interface potential).

The real free energy of transfer of ion from water to a second solvent ($\Delta \alpha_i = \alpha_i^s - \alpha_i^w$) has been determined from the measurements of Volta potential by Case and Parsons^{26,27} and using the value of α_i^w by Randles²⁵, α_i^s has been evaluated. Unfortunately this experimental determination is not free from criticisms. For example, the adsorption of water vapour in mercury can alter both the work function and surface potential.

The real free energy of solvation of an ion can be correlated to medium effect from the consideration of Born-Haber cycle as shown in the figure. The cation M^{z+} is removed from water to the gas phase and is returned to the solvent 's'. The standard real free energy change for the process is

Born Haber type cycle for the transfer of M^{z+} from water to solvent 's'.

$$\Delta \alpha_i^\circ = \Delta \alpha_{\text{solv}(M^{z+})_s}^\circ - \Delta \alpha_{\text{solv}(M^{z+})_w}^\circ$$

$$= \Delta G_{\text{solv}(M^{z+})_s}^\circ + Z\chi^s F - \Delta G_{\text{solv}(M^{z+})_w}^\circ - Z\chi^w F$$

$$= \Delta G_{\text{t}(M^{z+})_w}^\circ + ZF(\chi^s - \chi^w) \dots (3)$$

$\Delta G_{\text{t}(M^{z+})_w}^\circ$ values of ions cannot be determined experimentally. $\Delta \alpha_i^\circ$ of ions is amenable to experimental measurement but, as has been referred to already, it is not free from criticisms. It is however interesting to note that when one considers the properties of a neutral combination of ions, i.e., salts when $Z_M + + Z_X - = 0$ the real free energy change become equal to the Gibbs free energy change, namely,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \alpha_{\text{t}(M_X)}^\circ &= \Delta \alpha_{\text{t}(M^+)}^\circ + \Delta \alpha_{\text{t}(X^-)}^\circ \\ &= \Delta G_{\text{t}(M_X)}^\circ \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

So in order to arrive at a set of $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^\circ$ (ion), one often starts with the determination of thermodynamic properties of a series of salts.

The determination of "medium effect" of H^+ ions ($\log_m \gamma_{H^+}$) evoked considerable interest as it describes directly the relative basicities of two solvents⁶ and can be obtained from the direct measurements of the cell,

for which $E = -\frac{RT}{F} \ln_m \gamma_{H^+} + E_{lj}$ when E_{lj} denotes the liquid junction potential.

Bjerrum and Larsson⁴⁹ were first to determine the medium effect of proton. They used in their experiment a hydrogen electrode in the non-aqueous medium and combined it with a calomel reference electrode through a 3.5 N KCl salt bridge and assumed negligible liquid junction potential. Ojima⁵⁰, however, used Planck equation for the calculation of the liquid junction potential. The limitation of the validity of Planck equation in evaluation of as also the efficiency of the salt bridge in eliminating the liquid junction potential makes the determination of the ionic medium effect uncertain.

Models based on Born equation, its modifications and other theoretical approaches :

Considerable efforts have been put in attempts to evaluate the changes of free energies and enthalpies of single ion from one medium to another^{22,23,51,52}.

In the simplest form, the medium effect of ion 'i' is quantitatively described on the basis of Born⁵³ equation by the following expression,

$$\ln_m \gamma_i = \frac{Nz_i^2 e^2}{2RT r_i} (1/\epsilon_s - 1/\epsilon_w) \dots (5)$$

where r_i is the radius of the 'i' ion, ϵ_s and ϵ_w are the dielectric constants of the solvent and water respectively. As pointed out earlier this equation ignores the work of transfer across the interface. Further, no account has been taken of the effect of the change of the dielectric constant due to the strong field around the ions. The charge and nature of the solute may result in dielectric saturation of water in the vicinity of ions⁵⁴ and formation of a clathrate by water molecules in the vicinity of a nonpolar solute due to the hydrophobic bonding effects⁵⁵. Frank and Wen's⁵⁶ model of ion-hydration considers around an ion(i) a primary solvation zone where solvent molecules are immobilized by ions; (ii) a secondary solvation zone of disordered solvent molecules due to structure-making and structure breaking processes and then (iii) the structurally normal solvent molecules. The equation (5) which contains two

parameters-radius and bulk dielectric constant-has been modified incorporating refinements based on (i) the increase in crystallographic radii⁵⁷⁻⁶³ due to solvation and (ii) the dielectric saturation in the vicinity of the ion reducing the effective dielectric constant of the medium^{54,63-68}.

Introducing an adjustable parameter for the change in the ionic radii in solvent from that of the crystal radii, Voet⁵⁷ and subsequently Latimer, Pitzer and Slansky⁵⁸ proposed the following equation for the transfer-free energy associated with a cation

$$\Delta G^{\circ} t(\text{cation}) = \left(\frac{NZ_1^2 e^2}{2} \right) [(1 - 1/\epsilon_s)/(r_+ + R_{+s}) - (1 - 1/\epsilon_w)/(r_+ + R_{+w})] \dots (6)$$

where $R_{+(s)}$ and $R_{+(w)}$ are the appropriate corrections for ionic radii (adjustable parameters). This equation was applied with varying success by Koepf, Wendt and Strehlow⁶⁰, Strehlow¹³, Coetzee *et al.*^{61,62}.

The phenomenon of dielectric saturation has been considered by a number of workers. Graham⁶⁴ proposed an equation for the variation of dielectric constant with electric field strength, as described by the equation,

$$\epsilon_g = n^2 + (\epsilon_0 - n^2)/(1 + bE^2) \dots (7)$$

where ϵ_g is $d\epsilon/dE$, E the field strength at a distance 'r', n the refractive index and 'b' a parameter independent of E . It has been found that above a certain value of r , ϵ_g becomes equal to ϵ_0 and to ϵ_{sat} below a certain critical value of $r=r_0$. The radii for dielectric saturation of water and a number of alcohols are available²¹.

Hepler⁶⁵ used Hasted *et al.*'s⁶⁶ values $\epsilon_{sat} = 5$ for $r < 1.5 \text{ \AA}$ and $\epsilon_0 = 78.30$ for $r > 4.0 \text{ \AA}$ and expressed ϵ as a function of r as given by the equation,

$$\epsilon = [(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_{sat})/2.5](r - 1.5) + \epsilon_{sat} \dots (8)$$

The free-energy change of the hydration of an ion is given by

$$\Delta G_{el} = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \left[\frac{1.5}{r} \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \frac{dr}{\epsilon_{sat} r^2} + \frac{4.0}{1.5} \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \frac{dr}{(Xr - Y)r^2} + \int_0^{\infty} \frac{dr}{\epsilon_0 r^2} \right] \dots (9)$$

where $X = (\epsilon_w - \epsilon_{sat})/2.5$ and $Y = 1.5X - \epsilon_{sat}$.

The corresponding Stoke's⁶⁷ equation is

$$\mu_{aq}^{el} = \frac{NZ^2 e^2}{2} \left[\frac{2nr_w}{r_0(r_0 + 2nr_w)\epsilon_{eff}} + \frac{1}{\epsilon(r_0 + 2nr_w)} \right] \dots (10)$$

where $2nr_w$ is the thickness of n layers of water molecules around the ion, r_0 is the crystal radius, ϵ , the bulk dielectric constant, ϵ_{eff} the effective dielectric constant of the bound water as given by $1/\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{1}{2}(1/5 + 1/78)$.

These equations were used by Bates and coworkers⁶⁹⁻⁷² to calculate the values of ΔG_{el}° and the basicities of different methanol-water mixtures although these equations cannot explain the experimental hydration data, especially the differences in the hydration of cations and anions of equal size.

All these treatments consider the interactions of the ions with the solvent to be predominantly electrostatic and neglects specific solute-solvent interactions and non-specific "neutral" component of the solvation energies of ions. A complete understanding requires the knowledge of ion-dipole, ion-induced dipole, ion-quadrupole, dipole-dipole and London dispersion forces which are functions of r^{-2} , r^{-4} , r^{-3} , r^{-3} and r^{-6} in the same order where r is the corresponding interaction distances which contains the ionic radius term but not always equal to it^{73,74}. An actual calculation of solvation energies thus requires a knowledge of radii of ions and solvent molecules, the various interaction distances, polarizabilities, multipole moments of the solvent molecules and the ions, the coordination number of the primary solvation shell and also the various geometric factors which make the calculation very difficult and cumbersome.

The charging energy has been expressed in terms of a power series as in the equation

$$\Delta G_{el}^{\circ} = -\frac{Z^2 e^2}{2} (1 - 1/\epsilon) r^{-1} - Z^2 A r^{-2} - Z^2 B r^{-3} - Z^2 C r^{-4} \dots (11)$$

The constants may be calculated by the method of least squares for any solvent if sufficient experimental data are available. This method has been very little used.

Goldman and Bates⁷⁵ used an electrostatic model to calculate ΔG° ($\Delta G^{\circ} = \Delta G_{el}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{neutral}^{\circ}$), ΔH° and ΔS° associated with the transfer of seventeen ions from the gas to water at 25°C. The ions are taken to be charged conducting spheres both in the gas phase and in solution. Stoke's radii and Goldschmidt's radii have been used for the radii of the free gaseous ions and bare ions in solution. The primary solvation energies have been calculated assuming water to be isotropic polarisable spheres each containing a permanent off-centre dipole. The Born continuum treatment has been used to calculate the secondary solvation effects. $\Delta G_{neutral}$ has been considered to consist of the free-energy change associated with the change in volume. This model has, however, not been extended to calculate thermodynamic properties of transfer in other solvents.

A more rigorous approach has been made by Podova^{21,70,79} who used the fundamental equation for the free energy of a dielectric continuum in an electric field

$$\Delta G_{el} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int \int \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{\epsilon} \cdot d\vec{v} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

where \vec{E} and $\vec{\epsilon}$ are the field strength and electric displacement vectors respectively in a volume $d\vec{v}$ which is $4\pi r^2 dr$ assuming spherical symmetry of the field around an ion. The free-energy of the ion in solution compound to that in gas phase is

$$\Delta G^0_{solv.} = \frac{N}{4\pi} \int \int \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{\epsilon} \cdot 4\pi r^2 dr - \frac{Nz^2 e^2}{2r_g} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

Using the differential dielectric constant defined by

$$\epsilon_{\vec{a}} = \frac{d\vec{\epsilon}}{d\vec{E}}$$

and substituting in equation (13) we obtain

$$\Delta G^0_{solv.} = \frac{N}{2} \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \int \epsilon_{\vec{a}} d(E^2) r^2 dr - \frac{Nz^2 e^2}{2r_g} \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

where E_r is the field strength at a distance 'r' and r_0 is the intrinsic or effective radius of the bare ion in solution and r_g the radius of the ion in the gaseous phase.

Using Graham's relation,

$$\epsilon_d = n^2 + (\epsilon_0 - n^2)/(1 + bE^2) \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

we have,

$$\Delta G^0_{solv.} = \frac{N}{2} \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \int \left(n^2 + \frac{\epsilon_0 - n^2}{1 + bE^2} \right) d(E^2) r^2 dr -$$

$$\frac{Nz^2 e^2}{2r_g} = \frac{N}{2} \left[n^2 \int_{r_0}^{\infty} E_r^2 r^2 dr + \left(\frac{\epsilon_0 - n^2}{b} \right) \times$$

$$\int_{r_0}^{\infty} \ln(1 + bE_r^2) r^2 dr \right] - \frac{Nz^2 e^2}{2r_g} \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

The free energy transfer, ΔG_{tr} from water to methanol will be given by the expression,

$$\Delta G^0_{tr} = \frac{N}{2} \left\{ \left[n^2 \int_{r_0}^{\infty} E_r^2 r^2 dr + \left(\frac{\epsilon_0 - n^2}{b} \right) \times \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \ln(1 + bE_r^2) r^2 dr \right]_{\text{methanol}} - \left[n^2 \int_{r_0}^{\infty} E_r^2 r^2 dr + \left(\frac{\epsilon_0 - n^2}{b} \right) \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \ln(1 + bE_r^2) r^2 dr \right]_{\text{water}} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (17)$$

Calculated values of transfer free energy of HCl from water to methanol were found to be in reasonable agreement with experimental results.

Beveridge and Schnuelle⁷⁸ gave a general expression for the free-energy of an arbitrary charge distribution embedded in a spherical cavity surrounded by two dielectric continua, an extension of Kirkwood⁷⁹ treatment of reaction potential. The expression has been utilized by Abraham and Liszi⁴⁸ to calculate ΔG^0_{tr} of ions.

An ion of crystal radius 'a' and dielectric constant $\epsilon_1 = 1$ is considered to be surrounded by a solvent layer of thickness (b-a) taken to be the solvent radius and dielectric constant ϵ_{100} (=2) immersed in the bulk solvent of dielectric constant. The Helmholtz free-energy, A, of polarization is given by

$$A = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(n+1)(1-\epsilon'_a)}{(n+1)\epsilon'_a + n} \left(\frac{Q_n}{a^{2n+1}} \right) + \frac{(n+1)(1-\epsilon_b)}{(n+1)\epsilon_b + n} \left(1 - \frac{n(1-\epsilon'_a)}{(n+1)\epsilon'_a + n} \right) \frac{Q_n}{b^{2n+1}} \right] \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

where

$$Q_n = \sum_k \sum_l^M q_k q_l r_k^n r_l^n \sum \frac{(n-1m)!}{(n+1m)!} \times P_m^n \times$$

$$(\cos\theta_k)^{P_m^n} (\cos\theta_l)^{e - im(\phi_k - \phi_l)} \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

which reduces to

$$Q_n = \sum_k \sum_l q_k q_l r_k^n r_l^n P_n(\cos\theta_{kl}) \quad \dots \quad (20)$$

on using the addition theorem of Legendre polynomial where $P_n(\cos\theta_{kl})$ is a simple Legendre polynomial,

$$\epsilon'_a = \epsilon_a \left[1 + \frac{(n+1)(1-\epsilon_a)(1-\epsilon_b)a^{2n+1}}{\{(n+1)\epsilon_b + n\} b^{2n+1}} \right] \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

$$\epsilon_b = \epsilon_0/\epsilon_{100} \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon_a = \epsilon_{100}/\epsilon_1$$

The values of 'a' have been taken from the ionic crystal radii of Goldschmidt and Pauling. (b-a) has been calculated using Stearn-Eyring⁸⁰ formula from a liquid molar volume.

Yet another modification of Born's equation was suggested by Cobble and coworkers⁸¹ to calculate hydration energies. The critical interaction distance (radius parameter $1/R_s$) between the ion and the solvent is fixed experimentally by use of the observed free energy of hydration at 25°C. An

arbitrary entropy parameter C_s has been introduced to take into account both the loss in degrees of freedom of solvent molecules which form the hydration sheath of ions and also the changes in volume equal to the difference between the 'free volume' which the ions occupy in solution and their volume in the gaseous phase in the standard state of 1 atmosphere at a given temperature. C_s will not be very temperature-sensitive since the volume terms affect ion entropies as logarithmic ratios. The thermodynamic properties of hydration of a neutral ensemble of ions become,

$$\Delta G(T) = (-Ne^2/2R_s) (1 - 1/\epsilon) + C_s T \quad \dots (22)$$

$$\Delta H(T) = (-Ne^2/2R_s) \left[1 - 1/\epsilon + (T/\epsilon^2) \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial T} \right)_P \right] \quad \dots (23)$$

$$\Delta S(T) = (Ne^2/2R_s) (1/\epsilon^2) (\partial \epsilon / \partial T)_P - C_s \quad \dots (24)$$

$$\Delta C_p(T) = (Ne^2/2R_s) \left[(T/\epsilon^2) (\partial^2 \epsilon / \partial T^2)_P - (2T/\epsilon^3) \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial T} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots (25)$$

$$\text{where } (Ne^2/2R_s) = (Ne^2/2) (n_0 z_0^2/r_0 + n_a z_a^2/r_a) \\ = [-\Delta G_{Hydr. (295)} + 298.15 C_s] / (1 - 1/\epsilon_{298}).$$

The number of cations and anions in the neutral ensemble is represented by n_0 and n_a respectively and z_0, z_a, r_0 and r_a are the charges and radii of cation and anion.

Knowledge of $\Delta G(T)$ at temperatures or $\Delta(GT)$ and an enthalpy or entropy at any temperature fixes C_s for a salt. $1/R_s$ can be obtained by fitting the data in the equations. Once $1/R_s$ and C_s are known the thermodynamic parameters at any other temperature can be calculated. The authors claim limited success in terms of the agreement between experimental and predicted values of ΔH . A considerable amount of efforts has been put to the application of molecular orbital methods and statistical mechanical methods for making predictions about solvation processes. Some of the attempts in recent years are summarised here.

The quantum-mechanical approach is directed towards the simulation of explicit ab initio calculations for a complex between a solute molecule and one, a few or a large number of solvent molecules. They include the pair-potential method⁸²⁻⁸⁴, the electrostatic potential method⁸⁵, dielectric continuum models⁸⁶ and calculations in which the solvent environment^{88,89} is approximated by a dipole field. Noell and Morokuma⁹⁰ proposed a simple model of solvation in which the effect of solvent molecules is simulated by the inclusion of fractional point charges at the solvent atomic centres. The results of calculations of the hydration of Li^+ and F^- ions indicate that the point charge model is capable of predicting solvent energies.

The statistical supermolecule continuum model has been developed by Beveridge and Schnuelle⁹¹ to calculate the solvational energies of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , F^- and Cl^- assuming tetrahedral and octahedral coordinations.

Starting with the general expression for the partition function for the i^{th} configuration of the solute, when the site method is used for configurational averaging and multiple integration is replaced by summation for numerical calculations, one has

$$Z = 1/N \sum_{i=1}^N e^{-E_{ieff}(w_2 - w_M)/kT} \quad \dots (26)$$

Z is evaluated by Monte Carlo methods with N as the number of energy grid points, E_{ieff} is the energy of the supermolecule assembly of solute (1) and vicinal solvent molecules (particles 2-M) embedded in a polarizable dielectric. E_{ieff} is made up of the contribution from the dissolved ion and its first solvation shell E_i^{Sm} and a contribution resulting from the interaction of this supermolecular assembly with the polarizable dielectric E_i^{Pol} , the supermolecule and polarization energy.

E_i^{Sm} consists of $E^{i-w}(w_2 - w_M)$ and $E_{Sm}^{W-w}(w_2 - w_M)$, the first term being ion-water interaction and the second water-water. The supermolecule interaction energies were evaluated on the basis of the work of

Clementi and coworkers⁸³. E_i^{Pol} was estimated following Kirkwood⁷⁹. Helmholtz free energy A was evaluated directly from the partition function

$$A = -kT \ln Z \quad \dots (27)$$

and the internal energy computed simultaneously with Z as

$$U = \frac{1}{NZ} \sum_{i=1}^N E_{ieff} e^{-E_{ieff}/kT} \quad \dots (28)$$

The agreement between theory and experiment for statistical thermodynamic supermolecule calculation on hydration is within reasonable expectation.

In a recent paper Claverie *et al.*⁹² investigated the solute-solvent interactions using three different approaches, namely, (i) discrete model, (ii) continuum model and (iii) discrete continuum combined model.

From a comparative survey of results of calculation of solvation energies by the three methods these

authors conclude that the discrete model gives a representation of the 'structure' of the solvent molecules and provides satisfactorily the primary solvation sites. The continuum model gives solvation energy with good accuracy and the combination of discrete and continuum models should be especially appropriate for studying ionic species.

Methods based on negligible transfer free energies and equality of transfer free energies :

Electrode potentials in any solvent is expressed with reference to the potential of standard hydrogen electrode in that solvent (arbitrary zero). This, as pointed out by Popovych⁹³, generates as many thermodynamically unrelated emf scales as the solvents. Similarly the definition of pH ,

$$pH = (G_{H^+}^0 - \overline{G}_{H^+})/2.303 RT \quad \dots (29)$$

leads to as many pH scales as the media. The same nominal value of pH in different solvents does not

imply equal proton activity as $G_{H^+}^0$ would vary with

the properties of the solvent. For achieving a unified scale, the search for a reference electrode with the same emf in all solvents becomes imperative.

Pleskov⁹⁴ proposed that the potential of Rb/Rb^+ couple, because of large radius of ion and its low polarizability, should have the same value in all solvents. Thus the transfer free energy of Rb^+ ion is zero between any two solvents. Experimental values of transfer free-energy of halides of Rb^+ and Cs^+ in different solvents indicated the limitations of Pleskov's assumption. Strehlow and coworkers^{18,60,95} made allowance for the changed dielectric constant and suggested a modified Rb -scale which was used by Coetzee *et al.*⁹⁶.

Koepf, Wendt and Strehlow^{18,60,95} and also Kuwana *et al.*^{96(a)} chose redox systems with large symmetrical complexes, Ferricinium(Fic)/Ferrocene (Foc) and Cobalticene(Cic)/Cobaltocene(Coc). The standard redox potential of Fic^+/Foc in water and the solvent 's' gives the value

$$\begin{aligned} & [\Delta G_{t(H^+)}^0 - \{ \Delta G_{t(Fic)^+}^0 - \Delta G_{t(Foc)}^0 \}] \\ & = [\Delta G_{t(H^+)}^0 - \Delta G_{t(ol)(Fic^+)}^0] \quad \dots (30) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{since } \Delta G_{t(neutral)(Fic^+)}^0 = \Delta G_{t(Foc)}^0$$

Strehlow calculated $\Delta G_{t(ol)(Fic^+)}^0$ using the equation

$$\Delta G_{t(ol)(Fic^+)}^0 = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \left[\frac{(1 - 1/\epsilon_1)}{(r + a_1)} - \frac{(1 - 1/\epsilon_2)}{(r + a_2)} \right] \quad \dots 31$$

where a_1 and a_2 are constant specific for the solvents in question.

Despite the limitations that the method involves the assumption of elimination of the liquid junction potential by salt bridges⁹⁷, this has been used extensively by deLigny⁹⁹⁻¹⁰⁸ and coworkers. Because of the low solubility of ferrocene and instability of ferricene in water, the E^0 has been calculated from the polarographic half-wave potential of the process $Foc \rightleftharpoons Fic^+ + e$.

This method has been recently used by Kalidas *et al.*¹⁰⁴ to determine $\Delta G_{t(H^+)}^0$, $\Delta G_{t(Ag^+)}^0$, $\Delta G_{t(Tl^+)}^0$ in different MeOH-water, propylene glycol-water, methanol-propylene glycol, ethylene glycol-diethylene-glycol mixtures.

In addition to the uncertain liquid junction potential, the presence of large amount of indifferent electrolyte may change the solvent structure and thus the medium effects. Ferrocene may have residual electrostatic component of the ion and specific interaction of redox couples with water and other solvents are known⁶¹. There may be uncertainties in the crystal radii of ferrocene⁹⁸(3.8 Å) and ferricinium ion (3.3 Å)¹⁰².

Other redox couples studied are Ferroin/Ferriin¹⁰⁶, (4,7 dime-Ferroin)/(4,7-dime-Ferriin)¹⁰⁷, bis diphenylchromium (0/1)^{108,109}, bisphenyl chromium(1)/bisphenyl chromium(II)^{109a}.

Parker and coworkers feel that ferrocene/ferricene assumption is not valid when water is one of the solvents. They recommend cells of the type

for the determination of the medium effect. The salt bridge contains tetra-ethyl-ammonium picrate with cations and anions of large and comparable size. With no specific interaction with solvents as apparent from the roughly equal conductance in all solvents studied, the salt bridge is likely to have negligible junction potential. Parker and co-workers measured the potential of the Fic/Foc couple against Ag^+/Ag electrode in fifteen different solvents. On the basis of the values they justified their negligible E_{1j} assumption. Even if the assumption of the E_{1j} being negligible is accepted with reservation, the potential at the interface between solvent medium is characteristic of the two media and the energy involved in the transfer of ions across it cannot be overlooked. The determination

of ΔG_t^0 of divalent cations by Hedwig *et al.*^{88,86} suffers from the same drawback.

Extrapolation Methods :

Izmaylov¹¹⁰⁻¹¹², first to use the extrapolation method, assumed that all significant contributions to the solvation energy of anion are function of $1/r^n$ where r is the crystallographic radius and n could be one to four or six. For an infinitely large ion the solvation energy is equal to zero.

$(\Delta G_{M^+}^0 - \Delta G_{H^+}^0)$ against $1/r_{M^+}$ and $(\Delta G_{H^+}^0 + \Delta G_{X^-}^0)$ against $1/r_{X^-}$ (where M^+ stands for alkali cations and X^- for halide ions) were plotted to get

$\Delta G_{H^+}^0$ by extrapolation ($1/r = 0$). The plot of $\left[-\Delta G_{H^+}^0 + (\Delta G_{M^+}^0 - \Delta G_{X^-}^0)/2 \right]$ against $\frac{1}{r_{av}}$ where $\frac{1}{r_{av}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{r_{M^+}} + \frac{1}{r_{X^-}} \right]$ was also tried to

improve on the value of $\Delta G_{H^+}^0$.

The solvation of ions was also examined by Izmaylov as complex formation between the solvent molecules which could act as donors and the ions with vacant orbitals as acceptor. On this basis he

suggested the plots of $\Delta G_{MX}^0 = (\Delta G_{M^+}^0 +$

$\Delta G_{X^-}^0)$ against $\frac{1}{n^2}$, $(\Delta G_{M^+}^0 - \Delta G_{H^+}^0)$ against $\frac{1}{n^2}$

and $\left[\Delta G_i^0 + (\Delta G_{M^+}^0 - \Delta G_{X^-}^0)/2 \right]$ against

$\frac{1}{n^2}$ for different iso-electronic pairs like Na^+F^- , K^+Cl^- , Rb^+Br^- and Cs^+I^- where n is the principal quantum number of the lowest vacant orbital of the ion. Izmaylov considered the second extrapolation to be more reliable.

Feakins and coworkers¹¹³⁻¹¹⁷ used emf method to determine the ΔG_t^0 (the free energies of transfer from water to different solvents) values of HCl, HBr and HI and also of LiCl, NaCl and KCl and used the plots of the equations,

$\Delta G_{t(HX)}^0 = \Delta G_{t(H^+)}^0 + ar_{X^-}^{-1}$ where r_{X^-} = radius

of X^- ($X^- = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-$) and $\Delta G_{t(Mol)}^0 =$

$\Delta G_{t(Cl^-)}^0 + br_{M^+}^{-1}$ where r_{M^+} = radius of M^+ ($M^+ = Li^+, Na^+, K^+$) ... (32)

to get $\Delta G_{t(M^+)}^0$ and $\Delta G_{t(Cl^-)}^0$ by extrapolation,

the linearity of which was not good. This is what is expected since the plot of ΔG^0 against $1/r$ is based on oversimplified Born model, ion-dipole interactions (the term in $f(r^{-2})$) are too large to be neglected¹¹⁸. Das and coworkers¹¹⁹ suggested

that 'simultaneous extrapolation' to $(r_{X^-})^{-1} = 0$ of

the plots of ΔG_t^0 (HX) and ΔG_t^0 (HCl-HX) i.e.,

ΔG_t^0 (Cl^-X^-) against $(r_{X^-})^{-1}$ suitably aimed at

having least discrepancies in the extrapolated values

of $\Delta G_{t(H^+)}^0 - 2.303 RT \log M_s / M_w$ and $\Delta G_{t(Cl^-)}^0 + 2.303 RT \log M_s / M_w$ with respect to

the experimental values of ΔG_t^0 (HCl) should lend

an extra confidence to the extrapolation (error = ± 0.1 to 0.2 K cal/ion).

As suggested by Bjerrum and Larsson⁴⁹ and more recently discussed by Haugen and Friedman¹²⁰,

ΔG_t^0 could be split into ΔG_t^0 (el) and $\Delta G_{t(neutral)}^0$,

the latter being related to the energetics associated with the properties of the medium. The neutral component is equated to the free-energy of transfer of an unchanged species of the same size and structure as the ion, from one solvent to another (inert gas assumption). Attempts to take into account

the $\Delta G_{t(neutral)}^0$ have been made by deLigny and

Alfenaar^{48,98} and more recently by Kim¹²¹ and Abraham and Liszi⁴⁸.

The calculation of $\Delta G_{neutral}^0$ in terms of the

steps, (i) the free energy change required to create a cavity of appropriate size, (ii) the energy involved in the reorganization of the solvent molecules around the cavity into various layers, (iii) the energy associated with solute-solvent interactions, and (iv) the energy difference between the standard states from gas to solution phase, has been discussed by Pierotti¹²². In view of the difficulties involved in the calculation, deLigny and Alfenaar expressed the

free energy of transfer of ion in terms of $\Delta G_{neutral}^0$

and ion-ion, ion-dipole, ion-quadrupole interactions by the equation,

$$\Delta G_{t(\text{ion})}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{\text{neut}}^{\circ} + \frac{a}{r} + \frac{b}{r^2} + \frac{c}{r^3} + \dots \quad (33)$$

The free energy of transfer of a neutral combination (an electrolyte) would be given as follows,

$$\Delta G_{t(\text{M}^+)}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{t(\text{X}^-)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{\text{neut}(\text{X})}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{t(\text{H}^+)}^{\circ} + \frac{a}{r_{\text{X}^-}} + \frac{b}{r_{\text{X}^-}^2} + \frac{c}{r_{\text{X}^-}^3} + \dots \quad (34)$$

$$\Delta G_{t(\text{H}^+)}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{t(\text{M}^+)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{\text{neut}(\text{M})}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{t(\text{H}^+)}^{\circ} - \frac{a}{r_{\text{M}^+}} + \frac{b}{r_{\text{M}^+}^2} + \frac{e}{r_{\text{M}^+}^3} + \dots \quad (35)$$

$\Delta G_{t(\text{neutral})}^{\circ}$ were estimated from the plot of

$\Delta G_{t(\text{inert gas})}^{\circ}$ against r^2 which they justified on

the basis of Malsch's¹²³ experimental data and Buckingham's¹²⁴ theory. Plots of conventional free energies of transfer corrected for the neutral part versus $1/r$ were nonlinear. These were extrapolated to a common intercept and a, b, c, d and e were evaluated by a least square fit. The larger the ions the better was the accuracy.

deLigny and coworkers later slightly modified the equation used in the extrapolation, incorporating with Buckingham's¹²⁴ theory the ideas of Halliwell and Nyburg¹²⁵ and Muirhead-Gould and Laidler¹²⁶. The equation involved correction terms to the ionic radii two constants, dipole and quadrupole moments of solvent. $\Delta G_{t(\text{H}^+)}^{\circ}$ could be obtained only by optimization.

Salomon^{22,30,127} determined the individual free energies of solvation from the plot of the difference in conventional free-energies versus $(r_1)^{-1}$ where r_1 is the gas phase radii of Gouray and Adrian, in the form,

$$\Delta G_{\text{conv}}^{\circ}(\text{M}^+) - \Delta G_{\text{conv}}^{\circ}(\text{X}^-) = \frac{\text{constant}}{r_t} - 2\Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) \dots (36)$$

M^+ and X^- are ions of equal charge and radii.

$$\Delta G_{\text{conv}}^{\circ}(\text{M}^+) = \Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\circ}(\text{M}^+) - \Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) \text{ and}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{conv}}^{\circ}(\text{X}^-) = \Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\circ}(\text{X}^-) + \Delta G_{\text{so}}^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$$

According to Criss and Salomon, it is desirable to take the difference in $\Delta G_{t(\text{conv})}^{\circ}$ (ion) which automatically cancels the $\Delta G_{\text{neut}}^{\circ}$'s for anions and cations of equal charge and radii or at least reducing the difference in $\Delta G_{t(\text{neut})}^{\circ}$ to one of small magnitude.

Bax⁴⁸ *et al.* presents a comparative survey of the solvation energies of single ions obtained by different extrapolation methods. The uncertainty in ΔG° is about ± 0.5 (K cal/mole).

In a recent work Abraham and Liszi⁴⁸ estimated the free energy of solvation of univalent ion using one-layer continuum model for the calculation of $\Delta G_{\text{el}}^{\circ}$. For $\Delta G_{\text{neut}}^{\circ}$ which is the free energy of solvation of a nonpolar gaseous solute of the same size as the ion in question, they utilized the data on the free energy of solvation $\Delta G_{\text{s}}^{\circ}$ of gases and hydrocarbons in different solvents. They found for each nonpolar solvent a linear relationship between $\Delta G_{\text{s}}^{\circ}$ and r (the radius of the nonpolar solute up to 3.1A).

$$\Delta G_{\text{s}(\text{nonpolar solute})}^{\circ} = m r (\text{radius of the solute}) + C \dots (37)$$

m and c vary slightly with non-aqueous solvents. They calculated $\Delta G_{\text{neut}}^{\circ}$ for nonpolar solutes on the basis of solubility parameters. The authors claim good agreement between experimental and calculated free-energy of solvation of cations and anions in different solvents. The calculation of $\Delta G_{\text{neut}}^{\circ}$ is empirical.

Wells^{128,129}, on the other hand, attempted to calculate the free energies of the transfer of large single ions from water to water+ methanol with the 'neutral component' removed.

The change in proton affinity, P_a , for a species B in equilibrium with an acid A as in equation

on transferring the system from water to water+ methanol mixture is given by the equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P_a &= RT \ln(K_s / K_m) + \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}) \\ &= \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}) - \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{B}) = \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}) - \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A})_{\text{neut}} \\ &= \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A})_{\text{el}} \dots (38) \end{aligned}$$

Since for large ions A and B may be considered to be of the same size so that $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{B})$ can be taken to be equal to $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A})_{\text{neut}}$. For an unchanged acid A producing an anion B,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Since } \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}) &= \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{B})_{\text{neut}} \\ \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{B})_{\text{el}} &= \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{B})_{\text{neut}} = -P_a \dots (39) \end{aligned}$$

The values of ΔP_a have been calculated using the equation

$$\Delta P_a = 5.70(pK_w^M - pK_s^m) + \Delta G_t^0(H^+) - 5.7 \log \left(\frac{18.016}{M_x} \right) \dots (40)$$

with ΔP_a and $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ in KJ mol^{-1} on mole fraction scale, pK 's in molality scale and $M_x = 100/(W/32.04 + (100-W)/18.916)$, w the wt of methanol, utilizing the $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ previously determined. From the plots of $-\Delta P_a$ for the anion, Wells concluded that there is a structural component in the electrostatic free energy in addition to Born contribution. The authors have removed the neutral component in the calculation of the free-energies of large ions but in the expression $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ term is there. It is debatable how far $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ is free from such uncertainties as the author has tried to remove.

Method based on the equality of the transfer free energies of ions of reference electrolytes :

Grunwald and coworkers proposed this method which apportionates the transfer-free-energy of an (1 : 1) electrolyte equally between its large cation and anion. The central atom and the charge of both the cation and anion should be shielded by large organic radicals to minimize charge density and specific interactions with the solvent and as such the large cations and anions will have identical solvation properties. Tetraphenylphosphonium-tetraphenylboride $[(Ph)_4PB(Ph)_4]$ was the first reference electrolyte used by Grunwald and coworkers. $(Ph)_4C$ was chosen as its neutral analogue. Popovych suggested the use of tri-isoamyl-n-butylammonium tetraphenylboride $TABB(Ph)_4$ because of its equal Stokes^{136, 137} radii of the ions in different solvents like water, methanol, acetonitrile. The use of tetraphenylarsonium-tetraphenylboride $[Ph_4AsBPh_4]$ as reference electrolyte has been proposed by Parker and coworkers^{29, 32}.

All these three compounds comprise very large symmetrical ions with a central atom buried under insulating phenyl layers and are of approximately equal crystallographic radii. Because of their low solubilities these reference electrolytes are suitable for the determination of free energies of solvation without uncertain activity corrections¹³⁸. The use of reference electrolyte suffers from the drawback that errors may creep in from the possible formation of crystal solvates, ion pairs and micelle in solution. Equality of Stokes' radii or equal radii based on models may not indicate real indices of ion-sizes or imply a direct correlation between transport and thermodynamic properties. The apportionment of equal contribution by counter ions is difficult to justify in dipolar aprotic solvents which differentiates strongly between the relative solvation of cations and anions⁶¹.

Coetzee and Sharpe¹³⁹ pointed out that (i) the neutral component of $(Ph)_4B^-$ might also form a kind of hydrogen-bonding in protic solvents, (ii) the screening of the central atom in the phenyl substituted ions have enough open structure too inadequate to eliminate the solvation, (iii) phenyl groups undergo specific solvation¹⁴⁰ and that (iv) the difference between the ion-solvent quadrupole interaction terms for a cation and an anion treated in terms of Buckingham's theory is significant.

Attempts have been made to interpret the chemical shifts in the energies of solute-solvent interactions. Popovych *et al.* pointed out that NMR measurements are made with concentrated solutions where large ions would constitute an appreciable fraction of the solution leading to a perturbation of the solvent structure which may not be present in dilute solution.

In order to have an idea about the $\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut})$, Berne and Popovych¹⁴² studied the medium effect of tetraphenylgermane $(Ph)_4Ge$, tetraphenylmethane $(Ph)_4C$ and tetraphenylsilane $(Ph)_4Si$ which are excellent neutral analogues of $B(Ph)_4^-$, $(Ph)_4As^+$ and $(Ph)_4P^+$. Their results indicate that in the equation expressing the interactions the terms beyond $(r)^{-1}$ are unimportant.

Despite the limitations, the results by Popovych *et al.* using $TABP(Ph)_4$ and thereby Parker *et al.* using $(Ph)_4As B(Ph)_4$ are in good agreement considering that Parker uses formal solubility product while Popovych uses thermodynamic activity product.

Recently Kim¹²¹ made a critical study of use of Ph_4AsBPh_4 electrolyte assumption. The solvation energy of an ion is a composite of the electrostatic and non-electrostatic contributions. The former which accounts for interactions between the charges of ions and the multipole of the solvent molecules are calculated by Buckingham theory whereas the non-electrostatic part are replaced by experimental values of $\Delta G_t^0(Ph_4Ge)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(Ph_4C)$ where the neutral molecules Ph_4Ge and Ph_4C are proved to be by their size and structures, neutral analogues of the reference ions Ph_4As^+ and Ph_4B^- respectively. The sum of the two is then compared with the corresponding experimental values of $\Delta G_t^0(Ph_4AsBPh_4)$ in various organic solvents and reasonable agreements between values are observed. In the procedure the molecular volumes of different physical natures of the tetraphenyl molecules are determined and they are correlated with standard energies of transfer in an effort to support the postulate that the values of $\Delta G_t^0(Ph_4Ge)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(Ph_4C)$ are equal to the $\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut})$ values of the Ph_4As^+ and Ph_4B^- ions respectively. The partition of the values for the reference cation and anion revealed some differences in the standard free energies of transfer in most cases slightly greater for the cation than for the anion. However, the differences do not exceed

the relative error assigned to each value. The results support strongly the $\text{Ph}_4\text{AsBPh}_4$ assumption for the determination of thermodynamic value for single ions.

Treiner¹⁴⁸ examined the $\text{Ph}_4\text{AsPh}_4\text{B}$ assumption through the use of scaled particle theory as outlined by Pierotti to deduce that the assumption was not valid for transfers between water, propylene carbonate, sulpholane, DMSO, N-Me-2 pyrrolidone and perhaps also dimethylformamide, a conclusion so different from the observations of Parker *et al.* and Abraham *et al.* Abraham and Naschzadeh¹⁴⁴ reexamined the analysis of Treiner and point out the limitation of the scaled particle theory in the calculation of transfer energies of large ions. Tenne and Ben-Naim¹⁴⁵ also remarked earlier that it is impossible to apply scaled particle theory alone for mixtures of water and ethanol.

Miscellaneous methods :

1) Method based on Hammett Acidity function :

The Hammett acidity function¹⁴⁶ H_0 can be used to get the approximate values of $\log_m \gamma_{\text{H}}$ as discussed by Popovych⁴. The relationship between $\log_m \gamma_{\text{H}}$ and the H_0 for a nonaqueous solution of the acid HA of molality m_{HA} with a degree of dissociation, ' α ' is given by the equation,

$$\log_m \gamma_{\text{H}} = -H_0 - \log m_{\text{HA}} - \log \alpha - \log s \gamma_{\text{H}} + \log$$

$$\frac{s \gamma_{\text{BH}^+}}{s \gamma_{\text{B}}} + \log \frac{m \gamma_{\text{BH}^+}}{m \gamma_{\text{B}}}$$

$$= -H_0 - \log m_{\text{HA}} - \log \alpha - \log s \gamma_{\text{H}} +$$

$$\log \frac{s \gamma_{\text{BH}^+}}{s \gamma_{\text{B}}} + \log m \gamma_{\text{BH}^+}, \dots (41)$$

Since $\log_m \gamma_{\text{BH}^+} = \log_m \gamma_{\text{B}}$ for large indicator acids and where BH^+ and B are the acid and the base forms of unchanged Hammett indicators. Thus $\log_m \gamma_{\text{H}}$ can be approximated to $[-H_0 - \log m_{\text{HA}}]$ though slightly more positive under conditions when salt effects are unity.

Popovych prefers to estimate the order of magnitudes of $\log_m \gamma_{\text{H}}$ in alcohol-water and amphiprotic solvents from ΔpK values of cationic acids like anilinium or ammonium from the relation,

$$\Delta pK = \log_m \gamma_{\text{H}} - \log \frac{m \gamma_{\text{BH}^+}}{m \gamma_{\text{B}}} = \log m \gamma_{\text{H}} - \log m \gamma_{\text{BH}^+}(\text{el}) \dots (42)$$

deLigny¹⁴⁷, however, has pointed out that minor changes in the molecular structure of the indicator ions have profound influence on the electrical interactions between the indicator ions and the solvent.

ii) Method based on linear free-energy relations :

A method based on linear free-energy relationship has been proposed by Grunwald and coworkers¹⁴⁸⁻¹⁵¹ to determine the "medium effect" of H^+ ions in ethanol-water mixtures.

For the ionization of acids HA (aliphatic acids, benzoic acids) and BH^+ (anilinium ion, toluidinium ion) in alcohol-water mixtures and water, we have

$$(\text{pK}_s - \text{pK}_w)_{\text{HA}} = \log \gamma_{\text{H}^+} + \log \frac{\gamma_{\text{A}^-}}{\gamma_{\text{HA}}} = \log \gamma_{\text{H}^+} + m_{\text{A}} Y_- \dots (43)$$

$$\text{and } (\text{pK}_s - \text{pK}_w)_{\text{BH}^+} = \log \gamma_{\text{H}^+} + \log m_{\text{B}} Y_o \dots (44)$$

where m_{A} and m_{B} are substituent constant independent of the nature of the solvent, Y_- and Y_o are the solvent parameters dependent only on the solvent and

$$Y_- = (1-w^2) \\ \text{and } Y_o = -(1-w^2)$$

where w is the weight fraction of water in the solvent.

Now

$$(\text{pK}_s - \text{pK}_w)_{\text{HA}} - (\text{pK}_s - \text{pK}_w)_{\text{BH}^+} = m_{\text{A}} Y_- - m_{\text{B}} Y_o \dots (45)$$

m_{A} and m_{B} were determined by multiple-regression method which enables one to calculate $\log \gamma_{\text{H}^+}$

The limitations of this method have been pointed out by Wynne-Jones¹⁵², Popovych^{4,153} and Maity and Lahiri¹⁵³.

Although Parker is optimistic about the attainments in the field of single ion thermodynamics, there exists considerable difference between the results obtained using different approaches. Popovych *et al.* and Parker *et al.* prefer "reference electrolyte" assumption, deLigny *et al.* and Kalidas *et al.*¹⁵⁶ prefer ferrocene/ferrocinium approach while Feakins *et al.*, Criss and Salomon and Das *et al.* prefer different types of extrapolation with emf measurements of cells without liquid junction. A typical example of the variation may be seen in the values $\Delta G_{(\text{H}^+)}$ and $\Delta G_{\text{t}(\text{M}^+)}$ which change from a positive value on the basis of reference electrolyte assumption to a negative value by the extrapolation method.

Free energies of transfer from water to methanol at 25°C Kcal/mole

	Izmaylov ^{11*}	Feakins ^{11*}	deLigny ^{9*}	Strehlow ¹³
H ⁺	5.0	-3.01	-1.97	-0.99
Na ⁺	3.0	-3.04	-1.83	-0.55
K ⁺	2.0	-2.19	-1.22	-0.17

	Popovych ^{13*}	Case, Parson ^{2*}
	1.24	-5.84
	1.18	-5.90
		-5.2

Different methods have their limitations and naturally the results are likely to be different. The results show that not too much reliance should be laid on a particular method although "reference electrolyte" method appears to be the most reliable. However, Kolthoff^{15*} sounds a note of warning about accepting a value of ion medium activity coefficient obtained on the basis of any assumption with water as a reference solvent as the true value. As pointed out by Popovych⁴, the ultimate goal will be to compare the results of the various empirical methods with those calculated from statistical mechanical models for solvation energies on the theoretical side and with measured single electrode potentials on the experimental side.

References

- D. K. MEEK, in *The Chemistry of Non-aqueous Solvents* Ed. J. J. LAGOWSKI, Academic Press, New York, London, 1966, Part I, Chapter I.
- F. FRANKS, *Physico-Chemical Processes in Mixed and Aqueous Solvents*, Ed. F. Franks, Heinemann Educational Books Ltd., London, 1967, pp. 5-70.
- F. FRANKS and D. J. G. IVES, *Quart. Rev.* (London), 1966, 20, 1.
- O. POPOVYCH, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1970, 1, 73.
- R. G. BATES, *Determination of pH, Theory and Practice*, 2nd Ed. John Wiley and Sons, N. Y. 1973, Chapter 8.
- R. G. BATES, *Solute-Solvents Interactions*, Ed. J. J. COETZEE and C. D. RITCHIE, Marcel Dekker, New York and London, 1969, Chapter-e.
- J. H. SHARP and A. J. PARKER, *Proceedings of the Royal Australian Chemical Institute*, 89, 1972.
- A. J. PARKER, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1976, 21, 671.
- C. M. CRISS and M. SALOMON, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1976, 53, 763.
- A. K. COVINGTON and T. DICKINSON, Eds. *Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems*. Plenum Press, London and New York, 1973.
- E. J. KING, *Acid-base Equilibria*, Pergamon Press, 1966.
- FARADAY Discussions of the Chemical Society, No 67, 1977.
- H. STREHLOW in *The Chemistry of Non-aqueous Solvents*, Vol. I. Ed. J. J. LAGOWSKI, Academic Press, Inc. New York, 1966, Chapter-9.
- P. DEBYE, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 56.
- P. DEBYE and E. HUCKEL, *Physik. Z.*, 1923, 24, 186.
- C. W. DAVIES, *Progr. Reaction Kinetics*, 1961, 1, 161.
- E. GLUECKAUF, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, 51, 1235.
- R. A. STOKES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1870.
- B. D. STRUCK, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1977, 22, 1057 and references cited therein.
- A. J. PARKER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 69, 1.
- J. PADOVA in *Water and Aqueous Solutions, Structures, Thermodynamics and Transport Processes*, Ed. R. A. HORNE, Wiley-Interscience, 1972, Chapter-4.
- C. M. CRISS and M. SALOMON in *Physical Chemistry of Organic Systems*, Ed. A. K. COVINGTON and T. DICKINSON. Plenum Press, London, 1973.
- H. SCHNEIDER, *Topics in Current Chemistry*, 1976, 68, 108.
- B. B. OWEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 1758.
- J. E. B. RANDES, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 1573.
- B. CASE and R. PARSONS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, 63, 1224.
- R. PARSONS and B. J. RUBIN, *J.C.S., Faraday 1*, 1974, 70, 1636.
- J. ZAGORSKA and Z. KOCZOROWSKI, *Roczniki, Chemii*, 1970, 44, 1559.
- A. J. PARKER and R. ALEXANDER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 3313.
- B. G. COX, G. R. HEDWIG, A. J. PARKER and D. W. WATTS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 477.
- R. ALEXANDER E.C.F. KO, Y. C. MAC and A. J. PARKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 3703.
- R. ALEXANDER and A. J. PARKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 88, 5549.
- R. ALEXANDER, D. A. OWANSBY, A. J. PARKER and W. E. WAGHORNE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 933.
- D. A. OWENSBY, A. J. PARKER and J. W. DIGGLE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 96, 2682.
- G. R. HEDWIG and A. J. PARKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 96, 6589.
- G. R. HEDWIG and D. A. OWENSBY and A. J. PARKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 97, 3888.
- B. G. COX, R. NATARAJAN and W. S. WAGHORNE, *J.C.S., Faraday 1*, 1979, 75, 86.
- B. G. COX, W. E. WAGHORNE and C. K. PIGGOT, *J.C.S. Faraday 1*, 1974, 75, 227.
- M. SALOMON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 2519; 1975, 79, 429, 2000.
- M. H. ABRAHAM, *J.C.S. Faraday 1*, 1973, 69, 1375.
- M. H. ABRAHAM and A. F. DANIEL DE NAMOR, *J.C.S. Faraday 1*, 1976, 72, 955.
- M. H. ABRAHAM, E. AH-SING, A. F. DANIEL DE NAMOR, T. HILL, A. NASHZDEH and R. A. SCHULZ, *J.C.S. Faraday 1*, 1976, 72, 955.
- M. H. ABRAHAM and J. LISZI, *J.C.S. Faraday 1*, 1978, 74, 1604, 2858.
- M. H. ABRAHAM and A. F. DANIEL DE NAMOR, *J.C.S. Faraday 1*, 1978, 74, 2101.
- M. H. ABRAHAM, A. F. DANIEL DE NAMOR and R. A. SCHULZ, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, 5, 529; 1977, 6, 491.
- C. M. CRISS and E. LIKSHA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 2966.
- C. M. CRISS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 78, 1000.
- D. BAX, C.L. DE LIGNY and M. ALFENAAR, *Rec. Trans. Chim.*, 1972, 91, 452.
- N. BJERRUM and S. LARSSON, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1927, 127, 358.
- I. R. OIWA, *Sci. Rpt. Tohoku Univ., First. Ser.*, 1957, 41, 129.
- H. L. FRIEDMAN and C. V. KRISHNAN in *water*, Ed. F. FRANKS, Plenum Press, London, 1973, Vol. 3, Chapter-1.
- P. P. SCHMIDT, *J.C.S., Faraday II*, 1976, 72, 1048.
- M. BORN, *Z. Physik*, 1920, 1, 45.
- R. M. NOYES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 513; 1964, 86, 971.
- W. KAUZMANN, *Adv. Protein. Chem.*, 1959, 14, 1.
- H. S. FRANK and W. V. WEN, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 133.
- A. VOET, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 1301.
- W. W. LATIMER, K. S. FITZER and C. M. SLANSKY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 108.
- R. E. POWELL and W. M. LATIMER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, 19, 1139.
- H. M. KOEPP, H. WENDT and H. STREHLOW, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1960, 64, 483.

61. J. F. COETZEE and J. J. CAMPION, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2573.
62. J. F. COETZEE, J. M. SIMON and R. J. BERTOZZI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 766.
63. E. GLUECKAUF, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 572.
64. D. C. GRAHAME, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 903.
65. L. G. HEPLER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 587.
66. J. B. HASTED, D. M. RITSON and C. H. COLLIE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, **16**, 1.
67. R. H. STOKES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 971.
68. W. A. MILLEN and D. W. WATTS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 6501.
69. M. WOODHEAD, M. PAABO, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1964, **A68**, 305.
70. M. PAABO, R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 247.
71. R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON in *Chemical Physics of Ionic Solutions*, Ed. B. E. CONWAY and R. G. BARRADAS, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1966, Chapter-12.
72. R. G. BATES, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1971, **29**, 1.
73. J. S. MUIRHEAD-GOULD and K. J. LAIDLER in *Chemical Physics of Ionic Solutions*, Ed. B. E. CONWAY and R. G. BARRADAS, John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, 1966, Chapter-6.
74. D. R. ROSSEINSKY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 467.
75. S. GOLDMAN and R. G. BATES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 1476.
76. J. PADOVA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 692.
77. J. PADOVA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **39**, 1552; 1972, **56**, 1606.
78. D. L. BEVERIDGE and G. W. SCHNUELLE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 2562.
79. J. G. KIRKWOOD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **2**, 351.
80. A. E. STEARN and H. EYRING, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, **5**, 113.
81. J. W. COBBLE and R. C. MURRAY, Jr., *Faraday Discussions of the Chemical Society*, 1978, **64**, 144.
82. K. G. BREITSCHWERDT and H. KISTENMACHER, *Chem. Phys. Letters*, 1972, **14**, 288.
83. H. KISTENMACHER, H. POPKIE and E. CLEMENTI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **59**, 1325, 5842.
84. P. A. KELLMAN and I. D. KUNTZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 4766.
85. C. N. I. PORT and A. PULLMAN, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **31**, 231.
86. J. HYLTON, R. E. CHRISTOFFERSON and G. C. HALL, *Chem. Phys. Letters*, 1974, **26**, 501.
87. R. E. BURTON and J. DALY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **66**, 1281, 2408.
88. S. VAMABE, S. KATO, H. FUJIMOTO and K. FUKUI, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **30**, 327.
89. S. RAY, *Chem. Phys. Letters*, 1971, **11**, 573.
90. J. O. NOELL and K. MOROKUMA, *Chem. Phys. Letters*, 1975, **36**, 465.
91. G. W. SCHNUELLE and D. L. BEVERIDGE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 2566.
92. P. CLAVERIE, J. P. DAUDEY, J. LANGLET, B. PULLMAN, D. PIAZZOLA and M. J. HURON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 405.
93. O. POPOVYCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1974, **46**, 2009.
94. V. A. PLESKOV, *Usp. Khim.*, 1947, **16**, 254.
95. H. STREHLow, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1952, **56**, 827.
96. J. F. COETZEE, D. K. MCGURIE and J. L. HEDRICK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 1814.
96. a) T. KUWANA, D. E. BUBLITZ and G. HOH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5811.
97. (i) B. NAYAK, S. ADITYA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 925.
97. (ii) G. VALENZI, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1972, **31**, 547.
98. M. ALFENAAR and C. L. DE LIGNY, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1867, **86**, 925.
99. C. L. DE LIGNY, D. BAX, M. ALFENAAR and MISS M.G.L. ELFERINK, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1969, **88**, 1183.
100. C. L. DE LIGNY, MISS H.J.M. DENESSEN and M. ALFENAAR, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1971, **90**, 1265.
101. D. BAX, C. L. DE LIGNY, M. ALFENAAR and N. J. MOHR, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1972, **91**, 601.
102. D. BAX, C. L. DE LIGNY and A.G. REMIJNSE, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1972, **91**, 965, 1225.
103. D. BAX, Thesis, University of Utrecht, 1972.
104. C. KALIDAS, P. SIVAPRODAS and U. V. VENKATRAM, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, **32a**, 791.
105. M. ALFENAAR, C. L. DE LIGNY and A. G. REMIJNSE, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1967, **86**, 986.
106. I. M. KOLTHOFF and F. G. THOMAS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 3049.
107. J. V. NELSON and R. T. IWAMOTO, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **33**, 1975; 1963, **35**, 867.
108. H. P. SHROER and A. A. VLEEK, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1964, **334**, 205.
109. V. GUTTMAN and E. WYCHERA, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1966, **2**, 257.
109. (a) G. GRILZNER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1977, **24**, 5.
110. N. A. IZMAYLOV, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **34**, 1142.
111. N. A. IZMAYLOV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1959, **126**, 1033; 1963, **149**, 884, 1103, 1364.
112. N. A. IZMAYLOV, *Electrochemistry of Solutions*, Kharkov University Press, 1959.
113. D. FEAKINS and P. WATSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4686, 4734.
114. D. FEAKINS and D. J. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4986.
115. H. P. BENNETTO, D. FEAKINS and K. G. LAWRENCE, *J. Chem. (A)*, 1968, 1493.
116. A. L. ANDREWS, H. P. BENNETTO, D. FEAKINS, K. G. LAWRENCE and R. P. T. TOMKINS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1486.
117. D. FEAKINS, *Physico-Chemical Processes and Mixed Aqueous Solvents*, Ed. F. FRANKS, Heinemann Educational Books Ltd. London 1967, pp. 71-90.
118. a. B. E. CONWAY, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **17**, 481.
119. K. K. KUNDU, D. JANA and M.N. DAS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 2625.
120. G. R. HAUGEN and K. L. FREEDMAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4549.
121. J. I. KIM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 191.
122. R. A. PIERROTTI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 281.
123. J. MALSCH, *Physik. Z.*, 1929, **30**, 837.
124. A. D. BUCKINGHAM, *Discussions Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 151.
125. H. F. HALLIWEL and S. C. NYBURG, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 1126.
126. J. S. MUIRHEAD-GOULD and K. J. LAIDLER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 944.
127. M. SALOMON, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1971, **118**, 1609.
128. C. F. WELLS, *J.C.S. Faraday I*, 1978, **74**, 636.
129. C. F. WELLS, *J.C.S. Faraday I*, 1973, **69**, 984; 1974, **70**, 694; 1975, **71**, 1868; 1976, **72**, 601.
130. C. F. WELLS, *Faraday Discussions of the Chemical Society*, No. 64, 1977, pp. 248-249.
131. E. GRUNWALD, G. BAUGHMAN and G. KOHNSTAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5801.
132. O. POPOVYCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 558.
133. O. POPOVYCH and A. J. DILL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 456.
134. A. J. DILL and O. POPOVYCH, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1969, **14**, 240.
135. O. POPOVYCH and R. M. FRIEDMAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 1671.
136. (i) M. A. COPLAN and R. M. FOUSS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 1177.
136. (ii) J. F. SKINNER and R. M. FOUSS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 1882.
137. J. F. COETZEE and G. P. CUNNINGHAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 2529.
138. S. ADITYA and R. C. DAS, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1977, **36**, 206.
139. J. F. COETZEE and W. R. SHARPE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 3141.
140. C. V. KRISHMAN and H. L. FRIEDMAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 3934.
141. O. POPOVYCH, A. GIBOFSKY and D. H. BERNE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **44**, 811.

142. D. H. BERNE and O. POPOVYCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1972, 44, 817.
143. C. TREINER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 682.
144. M. H. ABRAHAM and A. NASCHZADEH, *Can. J. Chem.* 1979, 57, 71.
145. R. TENNE and A. BEN NAIM, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1977, 67, 4632.
146. L. P. HAMMETT and A. J. DEYRUP, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2721.
147. C. L. DELIGNY, H. LORIAUX and A. RUITER, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1961, 80, 725.
148. E. GRUNWALD and S. WINSTEIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 846.
149. E. GRUNWALD and B. J. BERKOWITZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4939.
150. E. GUTBEZAHL and E. GRUNWALD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 559, 565.
151. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, *Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions*, Wiley, New York, 1963.
152. LORD WYNNE-JONES in *Hydrogen-bonded Solvent Systems*, Ed. A. K. COVINGTON and P. JONES, Taylor and Francis, London, 1964.
153. S. K. MAITY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, (Leipzig) in press.
154. V. SRINIVAS RAO and C. KALIDAS, *Indian J. Chem.* 1975, 13, 1303.
155. I. M. KOLTHOFF and M. K. CHANTOONI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 7104.